

FROM HYPHENATION TO DE-HYPHENATION: INDIA'S EVOLVING RESPONSE TO THE ISRAEL-PALESTINE CONFLICT

Farheen Zia

PhD Scholar

Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi

farheenzia23@gmail.com

Abstract

There is no conflict in global history that has gathered as much international attention as the 'Israel-Palestine conflict.' Although, the international community has made several attempts to mediate and find a solution to this problem, but its unceasing nature, long history, and complexity have made it a central issue of debate and discussion among various states and non-state actors. While the major powers have been crystal clear about which side they support or condemn, India's 'de-hyphenated' response and stance towards the ongoing conflict is a subject of interest and often sparks debate in the national and global political landscape. It reflects a significant evolution and shift from a pro-Palestine stance rooted in anti-colonial principles to a more nuanced, balanced approach. This paper aims to provide an in-depth analysis of India's changing response to the Israel-Palestine conflict along with the strategic, geopolitical, and economic considerations guiding India's flexible position on the issue over the years.

Keywords: India, Israel-Palestine Conflict, Foreign Policy, De-hyphenation

Introduction

On 7th October 2023, the pro-Palestine militant group ' Hamas ' shattered the territory of Israel by a surprise attack. As a response, Israel's Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu promised to retaliate and declared war against Hamas. The unprecedented attack also raised concerns among the international community, compelling the world leaders to respond. Israel's western allies including the US, France, Italy, and Britain released a joint statement condemning the attack by Hamas, expressing

their ‘steadfast and united support’ for Israel. On the other hand, the Middle Eastern states such as Saudi Arabia, UAE, Qatar, Bahrain and Egypt saw the attack as a reaction to the prolonged occupation of Palestinian territory and expressed their deep concerns regarding the escalation of Israel’s military forces in the Gaza Strip (Khalil, 2023). The other major powers such as Russia and China held ambiguous positions, making their stances somewhat unclear and obscure. While Russia decided to remain silent by not releasing any official statement, the Chinese Foreign Ministry emphasised the need for peace talks between both parties (Israel and Palestine) to resolve the issue (Rumley & Redlich, 2023).

In South Asia, the international pressure to choose a side was intense for the Indian state. There’s no denying that India is not only a leading power in the subcontinent but also one of the fastest-emerging global powers in the international arena and that is why India’s position on Hamas’s attack was particularly significant from a global standpoint. Therefore, Prime Minister Narendra Modi made it clear in his statement that ‘India stands in solidarity with Israel in this difficult hour and called it a ‘terrorist attack’ on Israel (Modi, 2023). In the international sphere, PM Modi’s strong condemnation of Hamas was perceived as a pro-Israel stance inviting criticism by the opposition, pro-Palestinian groups, human rights experts, etc. In the Second Virtual Voice of Global South Summit held in November 2023 PM Modi clarified India’s stance and firmly condemned the deaths of Palestinian civilians, highlighting India’s commitment to finding a peaceful solution to the crisis. Moreover, India sent relief material to the Palestinians after the Prime Minister held talks with President Mahmoud Abbas of Palestine (Bhattacharjee, 2023). This act of balancing between Israel and Palestine is a critical point of departure from India’s pro-Palestine diplomatic approach to a more nuanced, balanced approach towards the Israel-Palestine conflict.

Resonating with anti-colonial principles, India’s foreign policymakers adopted an anti-imperialist ‘pro-Palestine’ approach in the initial years following India’s independence. However, India’s response to the recent Israel-Palestine conflict marks a substantial shift from its traditional pro-Palestine ‘hyphenated’ policy which kept Israel at a distance to a ‘de-hyphenated policy’ i.e. maintaining individual ties with both Israel and Palestine. This policy change has come in light of increased cooperation

and intensification of India's bilateral ties with Israel in recent years. A de-hyphenated foreign policy approach provides India with wide discretion and flexibility, allowing it to balance between two rival nations without compromising its national interest. This paper, therefore, aims to explore the changing contours of India's diplomatic response to the Israel-Palestine conflict along with the factors guiding the policy shift.

Israel-Palestine Conflict: A Brief Overview

The Israel-Palestine conflict is often regarded as one of the most intractable conflicts in the Middle East that is rooted in a complex interplay of religion and politics. Most scholars study it as a conflict of modern history, but its originating roots can be traced back to ancient times. Although an in-depth analysis of a 70-years-long conflict is beyond the limit and scope of this paper, a brief understanding of the problem is important before analysing India's stand on it. This short background attempts to explain a brief history of the Israel-Palestine conflict including its origin and the subsequent critical events.

Israel, formerly known as 'Canaan,' is a land of religious significance where the Hebrews migrated between 1800 to 1500 B.C. Later, their descendants (Jews) formally established the kingdom of Israel with Jerusalem as its capital in around 1000 BC (Lamin, 2021). However, the Jewish population had to leave their land owing to the increasing religious differences with the Roman Empire. "The Romans renamed the territory 'Palaestina', which came under the control of the Arabs in the 7th century introducing a new language and religion which was Arabic and Islam" (Lamin, 2021, p. 2). Palaestina was later invaded by the Ottoman Turks who ruled the kingdom for almost 400 years (1517-1918). Meanwhile, the anti-Semitic movements against the Jews were rising across Europe during the First World War. As a reaction, the Zionist movement was established by Theodor Herzl in 1897 which aimed at creating a Jewish homeland in Palestine (Smith, 2017). "The British also courted international Jewish support by issuing the Balfour Declaration in 1917, which supported the concept of a Jewish homeland in Palestine" (Lamin, 2021, p. 2).

Following World War I, the Ottoman Empire's collapse led to the establishment of the British Mandate for Palestine in 1922. At the same

time, this period witnessed a large influx of the Jewish population in Palestine from Europe owing to the escalating Jewish persecution by Adolf Hitler, particularly in Nazi Germany. The increasing presence of Jewish immigrants heightened tensions with the Arab population of Palestine, resulting in violent clashes and riots in 1920, 1929, and 1936-1939 (Morris, 2008). To settle the conflict, the United Nations proposed a partition plan - the 'UN Resolution 181' in 1947 but it was rejected by the Palestinians as it allocated approximately 55% of the land to the Jewish state, including the fertile coastal areas (Elmalı, 2023). The proposal was equivocally accepted by the Jews on 14th May 1948, terminating the British Mandate for Palestine, leading to the establishment of an 'Independent State of Israel.' The day marked the beginning of a series of conflicts between Arab nations and Israel, popularly known as 'Nakba' (catastrophe). The 'Six-Day Arab-Israeli War' was one such significant conflict of 1967 in which a coalition of Arab states including Jordan, Egypt, Iraq, and Syria revolted against Israel. The conflict ended with Israel capturing territories of the West Bank, Sinai Peninsula, East Jerusalem, Gaza Strip, and the Golan Heights (Elmalı, 2023). Another crucial event in the history of the Israel-Palestine conflict was the 'Yom Kippur War' of 1973 in which Egypt and Syria launched a collective surprise attack against Israel on the Jewish holiday Yom Kippur.

Over the years, several Palestinian organizations and rebel groups have emerged to support the cause and liberation of Palestine. Two such organizations are PLO and HAMAS. The Palestinian Liberation Organisation (PLO) was formed in 1964 and it is an internationally recognized body that represents Palestinians, advocates their right to self-determination, and engages in peace negotiations with Israel. On the other hand, the 1980s saw the rise of an Islamic militant organization under the leadership of Sheikh Yassin – 'Harakat al-Muqawama al-Islamiyya' - also known by its acronym, HAMAS. Unlike PLO, Hamas' ideology is to employ violent tactics in their liberation struggle against Israel (Akbarzadeh & Baxter, 2018). Similarly, various peace agreements, treaties, and summits have also been initiated to resolve the issue, including the Camp David Accords (1978), the Oslo Accords I & II (1993 & 1995), the Camp David Summit (2000), the Arab Peace Summit (2007), etc. In addition, the Road Map For Peace was also introduced by the Quartet of Russia, the United States, the United

Nations, and the European Union in 2002 which provided a two-state solution for the creation of an independent Palestine state. The plan was based on a phased approach, involving three stages – cessation of violence, creation of an independent Palestinian state, and stabilization of Palestinian institutions (UN, 2003). The plan was accepted by the Palestinians under the leadership of Mahmoud Abbas, however, the Israeli government introduced certain conditions including the dismantling of Hamas, the waiver of Palestinians' right to return, monitoring of the process by the United States instead of the Quartet, and demilitarisation of the provisional Palestinian state (Elmalı, 2023). The asymmetric position of Israel reflected an insincerity in adopting the plan, resulting in its cessation.

The persistent failure of peace negotiations, the rise of rebel groups, and the lack of determination among the conflicting parties to resolve the conflict have complicated the process of a two-state solution. Moreover, frequent clashes between the two parties have resulted in massive casualties, deaths, and widespread destruction.

Evolution of India's Response to Israel-Palestine Conflict

From being pro-Palestine to tilting towards Israel to balancing between both, India's position has evolved considerably given its national interest, regional and global dynamics. This section will try to analyse the shifting trajectory of India's foreign policy towards the Israel-Palestine conflict since its independence.

I. Pro-Palestine Hyphenated Approach: 1940s-1990s

- i. In the context of the Israel-Palestine conflict, countries usually rely on hyphenated foreign policies i.e. simultaneously addressing the needs and concerns of both nations (Smith, 2017). Through this diplomatic approach, a state develops policies concerning two antagonistic states without necessarily taking into account their individual contexts or aspirations. India's stance on the Israel-Palestine conflict in the initial years of its independence reflected such a disposition.
- ii. Adhering to the anti-imperial and anti-colonial principles, the foreign policymakers of a newly independent Indian state provided unwavering support to the Palestinian cause by

recognizing Palestine as an Arab State, blaming Britishers for their partition proposal, and criticizing the forced intrusion of Jews in Palestine. However, it is essential to remember that India's support for Palestine dates back to its pre-independence freedom struggle (Tripathy, 2013). As American historian Leonard A. Gordon argued "The Congress, led by Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru for a generation before Indian independence, by Jawaharlal Nehru from 1947 to 1964, and by his daughter, Indira Gandhi since 1966, has consistently taken the Arab side in Middle Eastern or what they call West Asian question" (Gordon, 1975, p. 221).

- iii. Mahatma Gandhi was unquestionably the face of India's freedom struggle who firmly believed that the unity of all religions, classes, and sects was imperative for a Pan-India national movement. With the growing discontentment among the Muslim population regarding the British operations against the Ottoman Caliphate (a major Islamic sect) during the First World War, Gandhi feared losing support from the Muslim community. As a response, he supported the anti-British Khilafat movement in 1919 led by Muslim activists such as Maulana Azad, Ajmal Khan, Muhammed Ali Jauhar, etc. Gandhi's strong efforts to gather the wholehearted support of the Muslim community reassured the Muslim population that the Indian National Congress would consider their views, especially in matters related to the Middle East. Under his leadership, the Congress also approved various resolutions in the 1920s and 1930s concerning the expanding imperialism in the Middle East. In one such Resolution, the Congress clearly stated that it "emphatically protests against the reign of terror as well as the partition proposals relating to Palestine and assures the Arabs of the solidarity of the Indian People with them." (Tendulkar, 1953, p. 278). In his weekly magazine 'Harijan' (1938), Gandhi also clarified his position and argued that "Palestine belongs to the Arabs in the same sense that England belongs to the English or France to the French. It is wrong and inhuman to impose the Jews on the Arabs. What is going on in Palestine today cannot be justified by any moral code of conduct." (Tendulkar, 1953, p. 434). He also expressed his dissatisfaction with the Jewish quest

to create a homeland and opined that “The Palestine of the Biblical conception is not a geographical tract. It is in their hearts. But if they must look to the Palestine of geography as their national home, it is wrong to enter it under the shadow of the British gun. They can settle in Palestine only by the goodwill of the Arabs” (Tendulkar, 1953, p. 437). Gandhi wanted the Jews to accept their birthplace i.e. Germany as their home and resist the Nazis’ expulsion through non-violent civil resistance. Therefore, he suggested that “If I were a Jew and were born in Germany and earned my livelihood there, I would claim Germany as my home, even as the tallest gentile German might, and challenge him to shoot me or cast me in the dungeon: I would refuse to be expelled or to submit to discriminating treatment” (Tendulkar, 1953, p. 435).

- iv. India’s hyphenated approach became more profound in the immediate aftermath of its independence when the Israel-Palestine conflict was seen as an Arab-Jews conflict. Jawaharlal Nehru, being the first Prime Minister and first foreign minister, viewed the Palestinian struggle through the lens of India’s freedom struggle against British imperialism. Nehru also sensed some similarities between India and Palestine and wrote in one of his essays “In Palestine the problem seems to be one of Arabs and Jews ... That is a wrong and misleading outlook. It is a problem of a growing nationalism desiring freedom and being suppressed by imperialism. In this process, British imperialism, as in India, has tried to play off one community against another and set the Jews against the Arabs” (Nehru, 1938, pp. 136-37). Therefore, for Nehru, it was always the colonial rulers who perpetuated antagonism between the two communities and that is why he blamed the Britishers as the primary culprits responsible for causing a rift between Jews and Palestinian Arabs. As far as the Jews were concerned, Nehru held some sympathy for them and believed that Jewish settlement in Palestine was only possible through their cooperation with the Arabs, as for him Palestine was and should continue to be essentially an Arab country.

- v. Nehru's recognition of Palestine as an Arab state was a vital factor that shaped India's foreign policy in favour of the Middle East in general and Palestine in particular during the Cold War. This is evident from the fact that India was always at the forefront when it came to voting in favour of Palestine at the United Nations. In 1947, India voted against UN 'Resolution 181' which proposed the division of Palestine into two separate states. Since India opposed the partition of India on religious grounds, it was also against the partition of Palestine on similar grounds (Gordon, 1975). Similarly, India also refused to accept Israel's membership in the UN and voted against it as "India could not recognize a state which had been achieved through the force of arms and not through negotiations" (Vincent, 2007, p. 159). It was in 1950 when India formally recognised the state of Israel but refrained from establishing diplomatic ties, and continued supporting Palestine.
- vi. Besides the UN, India leveraged its position at NAM to support anti-colonial movements around the world including the Palestinians' liberation struggle. Being one of the founding members of the Non-Aligned Movement, India strongly advocated for the rights of Palestinians at various NAM summits. At the Bandung Conference, Nehru supported the rights of the Arab people of Palestine and called for the implementation of the UN Resolutions (Tripathy, 2013). Similarly, the Cairo Summit (1964) also reiterated the right of self-determination of Palestinians with the members extending full support to the Palestinians in their struggle for liberation from colonialism and racism (Cairo Declaration, 1964, p. 10). In 1966 when Indira Gandhi became the Prime Minister, there were concerns that India would change its policy after the death of Palestine's staunch supporter Pandit Nehru. However, Mrs. Gandhi followed the footsteps of her father and India retained its support for Palestine. Under her leadership, India sided with its Arab allies at the UN Security Council on the Arab-Israeli conflict of 1967 and 1973, blaming Israel for escalating tensions in West Asia. Further, India became the first non-Arab state to recognize the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) in 1975 (Samuel & Rajiv, 2016). It also co-sponsored a draft UNGA

resolution to encourage the participation of PLO in the deliberations of the General Assembly on Palestinian issues.

II. A Shift Towards Israel in the 1990s:

vii. The end of the Cold War brought drastic changes in the social, political, and economic aspects of the world and marked the beginning of a new liberalized world order. Consequently, it also led to a fundamental shift in India's foreign policy towards Israel. The collapse of the USSR (India's closest ally) necessitated a re-evaluation of its foreign policy priorities. Moreover, economic liberalization required India to seek new partners and markets. In this context, India established full diplomatic relations with Israel in 1992. Although Prime Minister Narasimha Rao was the main driver of this change, the incremental approach initiated by Rajiv Gandhi helped pave the way for the normalization of relations by his successors in 1992 (Blarel, 2014).

viii. Rajiv Gandhi took over the command of Congress in 1984 after the assassination of his mother. Unlike his former counterparts, Rajiv Gandhi preferred to deal with India's foreign policy issues himself by directly interacting with the members of the Foreign Service, thereby transcending the traditional hierarchical framework (Blarel, 2014). He also wanted to diversify India's foreign relations without affecting its traditional stance on Palestine. As a result, Rajiv Gandhi brought significant changes to normalize India's relations with Israel. For instance, he met with Israel's Prime Minister Shimon Peres during the fortieth UNGA session in 1985 which was the first public meeting between two active Prime Ministers of the two countries (Blarel, 2014). In 1987, the Congress, for the first time, permitted Indian visas for Israel's tennis team to play against the Indian team in the Davis Cup Tournament (Kumaraswamy, 2002). However, these changes were not so efficient in bringing a complete reversal of India's policy towards Israel and India's one-sided support for Palestine remained unaffected. In a statement, Rajiv Gandhi clarified that "any failure to understand and accommodate the legitimate Palestinian aspirations through the process of negotiations at an international conference" would

only result in the “intensification of armed struggle to assert and secure Palestinian rights” (Asian Recorder, 1987, p. 19627) It was only after the end of the Cold War, that a significant tilt was observed in India’s approach towards Israel. A number of regional and global factors prompted Prime Minister Narasimha Rao to initiate this policy change. At the global level, the world was witnessing a wave of liberal reforms initiated by the IMF and World Bank. Considering the financial crisis of 1991, India was left with no option but to open its economic doors to foreign investors, especially the US (a crucial Israeli ally). Moreover, India’s economic recovery was also dependent upon receiving massive aid from the IMF and the World Bank where the US vote and influence were decisive (Blarel, 2014). As a result, an increasing engagement with the US inadvertently influenced India’s engagement with Israel. Besides, the former Foreign Secretary Dixit identified some crucial regional and domestic factors that pushed India closer to Israel in the 1990s. At the regional level, the Gulf War shifted the security concern from Israel to Iraq as Saddam Hussein emerged as a new threat in the West Asia. Moreover, PLO’s support for Iraq in the war was a major shock for the Arab states, leading to a rift between PLO and Arab countries. “The divisions in the Arab world over Israel and the PLO’s isolation were an opportunity for the Rao government to change its policy” (Blarel, 2014, p. 236). Further, the disintegration of the Soviet Union raised concerns about who could potentially replace India’s biggest arms supplier. The Gulf War had already exposed the superiority of US weapons, compelling India to find a potential defense partner having access to the US weapons and technology. Therefore, a partnership in the defense field was a crucial reason for the establishment of diplomatic relations with Israel in 1992 (Dixit, 1996). At the domestic level, the negative attitude of the Arab States on the issue of Kashmir was an unforeseen setback for India. At the behest of Pakistan, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) organised a fact-finding mission to visit Kashmir to report human rights abuses (OIC, 1991). On India’s refusal to enter Kashmir, the OIC condemned India for its violation of human rights in Kashmir in December 1991. The

Arab response came with a sense of betrayal for India that a pro-Arab and particularly pro-PLO stance had never been sufficiently reciprocated by the Arab nations. Dixit also criticized Arab states for not supporting India, especially during the Indo-Pak war of 1971. By critiquing India's handling of the Kashmir insurrection, the OIC provided impetus for India to reconsider its relationships with Arab states and Israel. Based on these considerations, India opted to move forward and establish diplomatic relations with Israel on 29 January 1992.

III. Initial Efforts of De-Hyphenation: 2000-2014

- ix. The bilateral ties between India and Israel further solidified with the beginning of the 21st century. Indo-Israeli cooperation in the fields of trade, defense, and tourism along with the high-level exchange visits among the delegates from both sides ushered in a new era of strategic partnership. The Ministry of Defense (MOD) listed Israel among its top five defense partners in its Annual Report 2006-07, hoping that this “rapidly expanding defense cooperation and ties.... will enhance not just the security environment in the region, but also the global security scenario” (MOD, 2007, p. 9). During this period, India also purchased crucial ammunition from Israel including airborne warning and control systems (AWACS), surveillance radar for the Indian Air Force (IAF), beyond visual range (BVR), Tavor assault rifles, etc (Samuel & Rajiv, 2016). In terms of trade relations, an exponential growth in bilateral trade was observed from 1992 when it was \$200 million which increased to \$6 billion in 2011-12 and \$5.7 billion in 2014-15 (Export-Import Data Bank). From 1993 to 2013, more than twenty bilateral agreements were signed between the two countries including the Cultural Agreement and Economic Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) (1993), Agreement on Trade and Economic Cooperation (1994), Indo-Israeli Industrial Initiative for R&D (2005), Agreement on Economic Cooperation (2005), etc (Blarel, 2014, p. 284). Additionally, the frequent exchange of visits between military delegates from both states facilitated communication and cooperation between the officials. From 2001 till 2015, at least eight defense chiefs from both sides

exchanged visits for consultations and to enhance mutual understanding (Samuel & Rajiv, 2016).

- x. The constant improvement of Indo-Israel relations in the first fifteen years of the 21st century could have appeared as a shift towards a pro-Israel approach, however, it is important to understand that this strategic partnership did not, by any means, imply India's isolation from Palestine. While normalizing relations with Israel, India maintained its support for Palestinian rights, thus leading to the emergence of a dual-track or 'de-hyphenated' policy. This de-hyphenation was reflected in India's continued effort to support Palestinians, despite the simultaneous strengthening of ties with Israel. In 2010, Prime Minister Manmohan Singh called India's support for the Palestinians "an article of faith for us. Our solidarity with the people of Palestine predates our independence" (Singh, 2010). At the same time, India consistently supported pro-Palestine resolutions. For instance, it supported Palestine's application for full membership status at the UN in 2011 and voted in favour of Resolution 67/19 to grant Palestine the status of 'Non-Member Observer' (Samuel & Rajiv, 2016). Similarly, the Indian government made substantial donations for humanitarian relief and developmental projects during this period. In 2008, India provided the Palestinian National Authority with \$27 million in grants (MEA, 2008). In 2009, it contributed 1 million US dollars as a regular donation with an additional 1 million to UNRWA for the reconstruction of the 'Nahr el-Bared' refugee camp (UNRWA, 2009). India also promised a \$10 million donation to Palestine during the visit of President Mahmoud Abbas of the Palestinian National Authority (PNA) in October 2008.
- xi. Besides economic and diplomatic support, India's position on the Israel-Palestine clashes in the first decade of the 21st century remained largely aligned with its traditional pro-Palestine stance. For instance, the Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) "condemned" the destruction of homes and the "indiscriminate use of force" in the Rafah refugee camp by the Israel Defense Forces in 2004 (MEA, 2004). In 2006, when the IDF killed nine members of a Palestinian family on a Gaza beach as a response

to a Hamas attack, India criticized the “unprovoked act and the killing of innocent civilians” (Samuel & Rajiv, 2016, p. 29). Similarly, when 1200 Palestinians died in a violent clash between Hamas and IDF in the ‘Operation Cast Lead’ the MEA urged “an immediate end to the use of force against Palestinian civilians in the Gaza Strip that has resulted in large numbers of casualties” (Samuel & Rajiv, 2016, p. 31). However, a subtle change was observed in MEA’s statement in 2012 when the IDF launched an eight-day operation called ‘Operation Pillar of Defense’ on which India responded by expressing “deep concern at the steep escalation of violence”, and urged “both sides to exercise maximum restraint” calling for direct talks between the Israelis and Palestinians for a “comprehensive resolution of the Palestinian situation” (MEA, 2012). This statement was significantly different from the previous ones in the sense that India avoided the use of the word ‘condemn’ to criticize the actions of either side. By refraining from making harsh statements against either side (Israel or Palestine), India chose to adopt a moderate stance towards the Israel-Palestine conflict. This position of India in 2012, was a breakthrough in its diplomatic policy, signalling towards a more consolidated de-hyphenated approach in the coming years.

IV. Consolidated De-Hyphenation 2014 onwards:

- xii. In 2014, a dramatic change in the Indian political landscape occurred when the Bharatiya Janata Party secured a decisive victory in the general elections and formed government under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi. This shift in leadership also brought a sea change in India’s foreign policy. In the context of the Israel-Palestine conflict, the Modi government adopted a more pragmatic, solidified, and profound De-Hyphenation policy. According to the foreign policy expert Ashok Kumar Behuria, ‘de-hyphenation’ in international politics implies dealing with two countries having an adversarial relationship independently. This approach helps a third country to build a relationship with one nation, ignoring the complexities of its relations with the other (Behuria, 2018). The de-hyphenated policy is often based on pragmatic considerations,

allowing a state to engage with two opposing nations autonomously instead of viewing them from a single hyphenated perspective. India's careful strategy of engaging with Israel and Palestine separately, to prevent straining relations with either, indicates the full maturation of its de-hyphenated approach in recent years. This de-hyphenation has been an integral part of post-2014 foreign policy where "India's relationship with Israel stands on its own merits, independent and separate from India's relationship with the Palestinians. It would no longer be India's relationship with Israel-Palestine, but India's relationship with Israel, and India's relationship with the Palestinians" (Sharma P. K., 2023, p. 11).

xiii. India's de-hyphenated policy for Israel and Palestine is characterized by two critical aspects. Firstly, the policy entails maintaining India's postcolonial identity by adhering to the non-aligned principles of the Nehruvian era. As part of this approach, India continues to support Palestine's right to self-determination and freedom from oppression. In responding to the military escalation in 2014, India's permanent representative at the Security Council Open Debate reiterated that "India's deep association with, and continuing commitment to, Palestine is rooted in our modern history that goes back to our struggle for independence" (MEA, 2014). In the same year, India also voted in favour of the UNHRC resolution that condemned Israel for its failure "to end its prolonged occupation of the Occupied Palestinian Territory, including East Jerusalem, in accordance with international law and relevant United Nations resolutions" (UNHRC, 2014). This demonstrates India's support for Palestine vis-à-vis its commitment to the NAM principles of anti-colonialism and anti-imperialism remains unchanged even under the leadership of PM Modi. The other essential aspect of India's de-hyphenation is 'equidistance' which involves a categorical separation of Israel from Palestine, thereby enabling India to normalize its relations with Israel (Pate, 2020). As a consequence, India abstained from voting on a UNHRC resolution in 2015 that condemned Israel for serious human rights violations and war crimes committed in military operations in 2014, particularly in the Gaza Strip, which resulted

in 1,462 Palestinian civilian deaths. The resolution also emphasized an urgent need to end the Israeli occupation that began in 1967.

xiv. Thus, by supporting the Palestinian cause in the 2014 UNHRC resolution while refraining from voting against Israel in the 2015 UNHRC resolution, India balanced its relations with the Arab World and Israel. Unlike the previous hyphenated approach of the Nehruvian Congress, India's contemporary de-hyphenation is primarily committed to strengthening bilateral ties with all the countries of West Asia and North Africa (WANA) region including Israel (MEA, 2016). The first Presidential visit to Israel by Pranab Mukherjee in October 2015 was a historic step in this direction as it resulted in the development of a roadmap for expanding Indo-Israeli cooperation in solar energy, education, water management, agriculture, animal husbandry, space research, and economy (Pate, 2020). Similarly, PM Modi's visit to Israel in July 2017 was another landmark event as it was the first time an Indian Prime Minister visited the country. Moreover, the trip was also exceptional from a diplomatic perspective. Earlier when any head of state visited Israel, he or she would visit the Palestinian Authority as well. PM Modi on the other hand, made a separate visit to the Palestinian state in February 2018 including the city of Ramallah in the West Bank. With this decision of PM Modi to visit Israel and Palestine independently, India's de-hyphenation policy became more apparent. At the same time, the strategy of 'equidistance' has also enabled India to carefully shift its stance from openly blaming Israel to adopting a more neutral position on the question of who is responsible for the conflict. Owing to the post-independence hyphenated foreign policy, India invariably viewed Israel as the originator and perpetrator of violence. 'Israel' as an actor, was thus, linked to 'Palestine' and the 'Gaza conflict' (Sharma R. , 2014). However, de-linking Israel from Palestine via de-hyphenation policy has significantly altered the traditional perspective and Israel is now seen as a democracy countering terrorism in the 'Middle East' (MEA, 2016). This is because India's sympathy for Israel as a victim of terrorism stems from its own experience with recurring extremist

insurgencies and terrorist attacks originating from the neighbouring states. For India, therefore, cross-border terrorism particularly emanating from Hamas is primarily responsible for the aggravation of conflict in the region. This is evident from India's response to the recent clashes in October 2023 where India chose to abstain from voting on a UNGA Resolution titled 'Protection of Civilians and Upholding Legal and Humanitarian Obligations' which called for an immediate humanitarian truce in the Israel-Hamas conflict. India's reason for abstention was based on the argument that the draft resolution lacked any mention of Hamas as the perpetrator of violence (Sharma P. K., 2023). As far as the statehood of Palestine is concerned, the 'two-state solution' has become a verbal acronym for India's policy of de-hyphenation whereby India seeks to promote a peaceful settlement of the Israel–Palestine conflict in a mutually agreed manner (Pate, 2020). Expressing the urgent need for a two-state solution, the External Affairs Minister, S Jaishankar reiterated "Certainly India has long believed in a two-state solution. We have maintained that position for many decades and, I think, today many more countries in the world feel not just that the two-state solution is necessary, but it is more urgent than it was before" (Abbas, 2024). Besides, India's humanitarian aid and concern for Palestinian civilians seem to remain unaffected despite its increasing proximity to Israel. This could possibly be attributed to the de-hyphenated separation of Palestine from Israel through which India has managed to empathize with the Palestinian cause without straining its relations with Israel. For instance, the Presidential visit of Mahmoud Abbas of PNA to India in May 2017 reinforced Indo-Palestinian bilateral ties and provided an opportunity to review the Middle East Peace Process. PM Modi reaffirmed India's support to Palestine in his press statement by calling Mahmoud Abbas an 'old friend' of India, highlighting India's unwavering support and assistance to Palestine since the freedom struggle and hoped for a sovereign, independent, united, and viable Palestine, co-existing peacefully with Israel (MEA, 2017). Responding to the recent October 2023 Israel-Hamas conflict, the Prime Minister also expressed concern for the civilian

casualties and loss of lives in his message on the occasion of the International Day of Solidarity with the Palestinian People on 22 November 2023 (Modi, 2023). The relief supplies were also dispatched from India following the October 7 attacks that resulted in a massive humanitarian crisis in Gaza. As a response, India sent 70 Tonnes of humanitarian aid including food and medical supplies, in addition to USD 5 million to the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees (UNRWA) till October 2023 (MEA, 2024). In this way, India's constant reassurance of support to Palestine has worked as a signal to the Arab world that India has never overlooked the struggle of the Palestinians.

- xv. Therefore, India's steadfast commitment to supporting the Palestinian cause while swiftly moving away from a pro-Palestine stance to a more nuanced approach towards the Israel-Palestine conflict indicates a careful act of 'balancing' which has become more prominent in the post-2014 de-hyphenated period.

Factors Influencing India's Policy Shift

While India's relations with Palestine have always been more or less consistently positive since independence, Indo-Israeli relations have soared to unprecedented levels only in the past decade. This change could be attributed to the 'explicit disassociation' of Israel from Palestine which became ostensibly visible in the Modi-led government as its West Asia policy stressed that Israel and Palestine were to be 'de-hyphenated' with neither of them impacting India's policy towards the other (R, 2023). However, India's growing engagement with Israel by advertently implementing de-hyphenation is itself influenced by certain geopolitical, economic, and strategic considerations including India's quest to become a global power. It is evident in an interdependent globalized world that India's aspirations to emerge as a major player in world politics cannot be achieved in isolation. In this sense, PM Modi's vision of 'Viksit Bharat' rests on the philosophy of 'Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam' which implies that 'the world is one family' and India's engagement is no longer limited to a particular region, it encompasses East, West, North, and South. Accordingly, India's growing bilateral engagement with Israel is seen from a prism of world engagement rather

than that of any particular region (Pate, 2020) Another area of mutual interest is counter-terrorism which also forms the base of Indo-Israel defense partnership is counter-terrorism. In a press statement, PM Modi acknowledged the shared experiences of India and Israel with cross-border terrorism and stated “We are aware of strategic threats to regional peace and stability. India has suffered first-hand the violence and hatred spread by terror. So has Israel. Prime Minister Netanyahu and I agreed to do much more together to protect our strategic interests and also cooperate to combat growing radicalization and terrorism, including in cyberspace” (MEA, 2017). Due to India’s heavy reliance on Israel’s defense technology and equipment, Israel emerged as India’s fourth largest arms supplier, constituting 9.5% of defense imports between 2010-2020 (Sharma M. , 2023). Similarly, India’s increasing economic and technological dependence has become a source of its growing economic partnership with Israel. In a jointly written blog, both the Prime Ministers, Modi and Netanyahu emphasized that “India is a growing economic powerhouse with a large market and talent pool. Israel is a world leader in high technology and innovation. The combination of India’s and Israel’s human resources and ingenuity will provide more effective and more affordable solutions for us in diverse fields that are priorities for both our governments: agriculture, water, health, environment, education, and security” (Modi & Netanyahu, 2017). Further, foreign policy analysts Sumit Ganguly and Nicholas Blarel also regard the decreasing hostilities between Israel and Arab states as one of the contributing factors to influence India’s shifting foreign policy. Unlike the earlier conflicts, the Arab states neither backed Hamas nor seriously denounced Israel in their response to the October 7, 2023 attack (Blarel & Ganguly, 2023). The moderate stance shows a pragmatism in the response of Arab states, which itself was an outcome of their increasing efforts to normalize relations with Israel through various peace initiatives including the recent Abraham Accords signed in 2020 between Israel and some Arab states such as UAE, Bahrain, Sudan, and Morocco. The decreasing hostility between Arab states and Israel inadvertently provided India with a diplomatic leeway to maintain its historical support for Palestine without straining its burgeoning ties with Israel.

Moreover, India’s cautious strategy of ‘balancing’ has also been effective in ensuring harmonious relations with the Arab world. The Arab League

Ambassador Yusuf Mohamed Abdulla Jameel on the anniversary of the Arab League's formation on 22nd March 2024 lauded India's support to Palestine and said "We appreciate India's principled stand towards Palestinian cause advocating for two States solution. By voting in favour of Palestine and extending humanitarian aid to the people of Gaza, India showcases its deep-rooted empathy and steadfast dedication to alleviating the suffering of those in need. In standing with Palestine, India not only upholds its moral obligations but also reinforces its status as a beacon of hope and solidarity in the global community" (Bhattacharjee, 2024). Since India is heavily dependent on both Israel and the Gulf states for its defense and energy requirements respectively, a de-hyphenated policy shift can be crucial in furthering India's strategic interests without disregarding Arab sensitivities towards Palestine.

Conclusion

India's evolving response to the Israel-Palestine conflict marks a significant departure from its earlier hyphenated approach towards a more nuanced and pragmatic de-hyphenated stance. The historical trajectory, characterized by initial staunch support for Palestine rooted in anti-colonial solidarity and non-alignment principles, gave way to pragmatic considerations in the post-Cold War era. This transition was marked by the establishment of full diplomatic relations with Israel in 1992, while simultaneously continuing to advocate for Palestinian rights and statehood on international platforms. Throughout the 21st century, India's approach has matured further under successive governments, culminating in a clear de-hyphenated policy framework which allows India to independently pursue strategic partnerships with both Israel and Palestine based on mutual interests. Prime Minister Narendra Modi's tenure has underscored this shift with landmark visits to Israel and Palestine, signalling India's commitment to maintaining balanced relations and advancing peace initiatives in the region. India's stance continues to advocate for a just and peaceful resolution to the Israel-Palestine conflict, emphasizing dialogue, negotiation, and adherence to international law. As India navigates the complexities of international relations, its evolving stance on the Israel-Palestine issue serves as a testament to its adaptability and commitment to promoting peace and prosperity in the Middle East and beyond.

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